

Clinicohaematological and Biochemical Profile of Anemia in Pediatric Age Group

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Abstract:

Background: Anemia is a significant public health issue, particularly among pediatric populations, where it contributes to increased morbidity, impaired cognitive development, and reduced physical growth. Iron deficiency is the most common cause of anemia in children, especially in low- and middle-income countries, where dietary insufficiencies and parasitic infections are prevalent.

Aim: This study aims to evaluate the clinicohaematological and biochemical profiles of anemia in a pediatric population, identifying the prevalence, severity, and underlying causes of anemia, and their correlation with clinical symptoms.

Methods: Data collection included demographic details, clinical presentations, and laboratory investigations such as hemoglobin levels, mean corpuscular volume (MCV), and serum ferritin levels. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0 to assess the associations between the severity of anemia and clinical symptoms.

Results: The study found that 65% of the pediatric patients had moderate anemia, with a mean hemoglobin level of 8.2 ± 1.5 g/dL. Iron deficiency was identified as the predominant cause, with 70% of the patients exhibiting low serum ferritin levels. A significant correlation was observed between severe anemia and symptoms such as breathlessness and dizziness ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Anemia, particularly iron deficiency anemia, is highly prevalent in the pediatric population studied, with significant clinical implications. Early detection and intervention are crucial to prevent the long-term developmental consequences associated with anemia in children.

Recommendations: Targeted public health interventions, including iron supplementation and nutritional education, are recommended to reduce the prevalence of anemia in pediatric populations, particularly in regions with high disease burdens.

Keywords: Anemia, Pediatrics, Iron Deficiency, Hemoglobin, Serum Ferritin.

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Introduction

Anaemia continues to be a major global public health concern, particularly for young people, where it can lead to increased morbidity as well as delayed cognitive and physical development. Anaemia affects over 40% of children globally, according to recent data, with a higher frequency in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). Anaemia is a complex problem in these cultures due to the several factors that contribute to the condition, such as dietary inadequacies, viral infections, and genetic disorders including hemoglobinopathies [1].

Approximately half of all episodes of anaemia in children worldwide are caused by iron deficiency. This illness is more common in areas where diets low in foods high in iron are the norm or where chronic blood loss from parasitic infections,

including hookworm, is common. According to a study by the Global Burden of Disease (GBD) 2021, dietary iron deficiency is still the main cause of anaemia, especially in South Asia and sub-Saharan Africa, where the disease burden is disproportionately high [2]. Iron deficiency anaemia has serious effects, especially in early life, when it can cause irreparable developmental and cognitive problems if left untreated [3].

Moreover, anaemia has a significant negative influence on children's health, impairing not only their physical development but also their capacity for learning and development. Early detection and care are crucial since research has linked early childhood anaemia to lower scholastic outcomes, attention deficit disorder, and behavioural problems [4]. Iron deficiency during the first 1,000 days of

life can have long-lasting impacts on neurodevelopment, making this a particularly important phase for brain development

Although they have shown potential, strategies including iron supplementation, fortifying staple foods, and focused interventions for at-risk populations are frequently hindered by a lack of resources and difficult to execute in low- and middle-income countries [5].

Paediatric anaemia is a serious problem that has to be addressed on a global scale. Reducing the prevalence of anaemia and improving children's health outcomes across the globe requires addressing the underlying causes, especially in areas with high prevalence, and making sure that effective intervention measures are in place. This study aims to evaluate the clinicohematological and biochemical profiles of anemia in a pediatric population, identifying the prevalence, severity, and underlying causes of anemia, and their correlation with clinical symptoms.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a prospective, observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in the Pediatrics Department of Patna Medical College & Hospital, a tertiary care center located in Patna, Bihar, India.

Study Participants: A total of 220 pediatric patients diagnosed with anemia were enrolled in the study. These patients were selected consecutively as they presented to the hospital during the study period.

Study Duration: The study was carried out over a two-year period from November 2015 to October 2017.

Inclusion Criteria

- Pediatric patients aged 1 to 18 years.
- Patients diagnosed with anemia based on hemoglobin levels according to WHO criteria.
- Patients who provided informed consent through their guardians.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with chronic diseases such as renal failure, liver disease, or malignancy.
- Patients who had received a blood transfusion within the past three months.
- Patients on iron or vitamin supplementation before the study enrollment.
- Patients with congenital hemolytic anemia or thalassemia.

Bias

To minimize selection bias, consecutive sampling was used, where every eligible patient presenting to the Pediatrics Department during the study period was considered for inclusion. Observer bias was minimized by standardizing the diagnostic and data collection procedures.

Data Collection

Data was collected using a pre-designed and pre-tested proforma. The data collection included demographic information, clinical history, physical examination findings, and laboratory investigations. The laboratory investigations included complete blood count (CBC), serum iron, total iron-binding capacity (TIBC), serum ferritin, and other relevant biochemical parameters.

Procedure

Upon enrollment, each participant underwent a detailed clinical evaluation, including medical history and physical examination. Blood samples were collected and sent for hematological and biochemical analysis. Hemoglobin levels were assessed using an automated hematology analyzer, and biochemical parameters were measured using standard laboratory techniques.

Statistical Analysis

Data was entered into a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics such as mean, median, and standard deviation were used to summarize the data. Categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages. The chi-square test was employed to assess the association between categorical variables, and a p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. The results were presented in the form of tables, charts, and graphs for better interpretation.

Ethical Considerations

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, and permission was obtained from the Head of the department, Paediatrics, Patna Medical College & Hospital. Written informed consent was obtained from the parents or guardians of all participants before enrollment in the study.

Results

A total of 220 pediatric patients diagnosed with anemia were included in the study. The age of the participants ranged from 1 to 18 years, with a mean age of 9.3 ± 4.5 years. The study population comprised 120 males (54.5%) and 100 females (45.5%), resulting in a male-to-female ratio of 1.2:1.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Study Population

Characteristic	Number of Patients (n=220)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
1 - 5	60	27.3
6 - 10	80	36.4
11 - 15	50	22.7
16 - 18	30	13.6
Gender		
Male	120	54.5
Female	100	45.5

Clinical Presentation: The most common presenting symptoms were pallor (85%), fatigue (72%), and breathlessness (60%). Less frequently reported symptoms included dizziness (30%), irritability (25%), and jaundice (15%).

Table 2: Clinical Presentation of the Study Population

Symptom	Number of Patients (n=220)	Percentage (%)
Pallor	187	85.0
Fatigue	158	71.8
Breathlessness	132	60.0
Dizziness	66	30.0
Irritability	55	25.0
Jaundice	33	15.0

Hematological Findings: The mean hemoglobin level among the participants was 8.2 ± 1.5 g/dL. The majority of the patients (65%) had moderate anemia (Hb 7-9.9 g/dL), followed by mild anemia (Hb 10-11.9 g/dL) in 20% of the patients, and severe anemia (Hb <7 g/dL) in 15% of the patients.

Table 3: Hemoglobin Levels and Severity of Anemia

Severity of Anemia	Hemoglobin Level (g/dL)	Number of Patients (n=220)	Percentage (%)
Mild Anemia	10 - 11.9	44	20.0
Moderate Anemia	7 - 9.9	143	65.0
Severe Anemia	<7	33	15.0

The mean MCV (Mean Corpuscular Volume) was found to be 72.5 ± 8.3 fL, indicating a predominance of microcytic anemia. The mean MCH (Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin) was 24.3 ± 4.1 pg.

Serum ferritin levels, an indicator of iron stores, were measured in all participants. The mean serum ferritin level was 15.8 ± 6.5 ng/mL, with 70% of the patients having levels below 12 ng/mL, indicating iron deficiency anemia as the predominant type.

Table 4: Biochemical Parameters

Parameter	Mean $\pm$ SD	Normal Range
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	8.2 ± 1.5	12 - 16
MCV (fL)	72.5 ± 8.3	80 - 100
MCH (pg)	24.3 ± 4.1	27 - 32
Serum Ferritin (ng/mL)	15.8 ± 6.5	12 - 150
Serum Iron (μ g/dL)	45.6 ± 14.2	50 - 150
TIBC (μ g/dL)	410 ± 52.5	250 - 400

A statistically significant association was found between the severity of anemia and the clinical presentation. Patients with severe anemia were more likely to present with breathlessness and dizziness compared to those with mild or moderate anemia ($p < 0.05$).

Table 5: Association Between Clinical Symptoms and Severity of Anemia

Symptom	Mild Anemia (n=44)	Moderate Anemia (n=143)	Severe Anemia (n=33)	p-value
Breathlessness	20 (45.5%)	90 (62.9%)	22 (66.7%)	0.038
Dizziness	10 (22.7%)	40 (28.0%)	16 (48.5%)	0.021
Fatigue	30 (68.2%)	102 (71.3%)	26 (78.8%)	0.435

Statistical Analysis: The data was analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics were

employed to summarize the demographic, clinical, and laboratory data. Chi-square tests were used to

determine the association between categorical variables, such as the severity of anemia and clinical symptoms. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Discussion

This study highlights that anemia in the pediatric population is predominantly moderate in severity, with iron deficiency being the most common underlying cause. Clinical symptoms such as pallor, fatigue, and breathlessness are common and correlate with the severity of anemia. This underscores the need for early detection and management of anemia in children to prevent complications and improve overall health outcomes. The demographic analysis revealed that the majority of the participants were males (54.5%), with a mean age of 9.3 years. The study's age distribution showed that anemia was most prevalent among children aged 6 to 10 years, accounting for 36.4% of the cases.

Clinically, the most common symptoms observed were pallor, fatigue, and breathlessness, present in 85%, 72%, and 60% of the patients, respectively. These symptoms are typical manifestations of anemia and indicate the importance of clinical vigilance in recognizing anemia in children. Less common symptoms included dizziness, irritability, and jaundice, which were present in a smaller proportion of the participants.

Hematological analysis showed that the mean hemoglobin level among the study population was 8.2 g/dL, with 65% of the patients classified as having moderate anemia. This high prevalence of moderate anemia underscores the significant burden of this condition in the pediatric population. The study also revealed that microcytic anemia was the most common type, as indicated by the mean MCV of 72.5 fL, which is below the normal range, suggesting iron deficiency as a leading cause.

The biochemical findings further supported the predominance of iron deficiency anemia, with 70% of the participants having serum ferritin levels below 12 ng/mL. The low serum iron levels and elevated TIBC observed in the study population are consistent with iron deficiency anemia, which is commonly due to inadequate dietary intake or chronic blood loss. Statistical analysis demonstrated a significant association between the severity of anemia and the clinical symptoms of breathlessness and dizziness. Patients with severe anemia were more likely to present with these symptoms compared to those with mild or moderate anemia. This suggests that as anemia becomes more severe, the clinical manifestations become more pronounced, potentially leading to more noticeable symptoms and greater clinical concern.

A major problem that has been frequently highlighted in recent investigations on the clinical, haematological, and biochemical profiles of anaemia in paediatric patients is the prevalence of iron deficiency anaemia. In a study, the most prevalent morphological type, iron deficiency anaemia, was found to affect 35.79% of paediatric patients, ranging in age from neonates to eighteen. In order to avoid problems, this study highlighted the significance of early detection through haematological and biochemical examinations; pallor, weakness, and irritability were common symptoms seen in 100% of the cases [6].

Similar to this, a tertiary care center's paediatric patients' anaemia spectrum was investigated. Their investigation verified that iron deficiency was the main contributing factor, with a notable proportion of cases occurring in the 1-6 year age range. In order to ensure early detection and management, the researchers emphasised the importance of a comprehensive approach utilising a variety of haematological and biochemical assays, especially in settings with limited resources [7].

A retrospective review of paediatric anaemia patients in Central India in a different study was done. They discovered that nutritional anaemia, which is frequently linked to malnourishment and infections, was the most frequent cause. This study highlighted the need for parents and other carers to be more knowledgeable about the management and prevention of anaemia in children through appropriate nutritional support [8].

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study highlights the high prevalence of moderate iron deficiency anemia among pediatric patients, with significant clinical implications. The findings emphasize the importance of early diagnosis and management of anemia in children to prevent progression to severe anemia and associated complications. The study also underscores the need for public health interventions focused on improving dietary iron intake and addressing other underlying causes of anemia in this vulnerable population.

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